

GUIDE FOR AUTHORS

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Manuscript: The manuscript should be typed double spaced on A4 size in Microsoft word and attached to a mail as a soft copy.

Organization of the Manuscript: The manuscript should be organized in the following order; Title, Author's name and address including E-mail address and telephone numbers; Abstract; Keywords; Introduction; Materials and Methods; Results and Discussion; Conclusion; Notation (If any); Acknowledgments; References. The main headings listed above should be capitalized and be left justified. Sub-sub headings should be in italics. All headings, sub headings, and sub-sub headings should be in bold font. Headings and sub headings should be identified with numbers such as 1; 1.1; 1.1.1 etc. For the sub headings, the first letter of every word should be capitalized.

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